

Supplementary Table S1. Statistics on all ORFs 60 nt or longer grouped by RNA type

Statistic	mRNA ¹	mRNA ²	ncRNA	rRNA	tRNA
Number of transcripts	44,624	44,624	5,657*	62*	974
Median length of transcripts, nt	1,280	1,280	413	120	75
Number of ORFs [#]	846,711	802,087	71,127	831	1,311
ORFs per transcript	19	18	13	13	1
Combined length of ORFs, nt	132,065,895	85,361,370	7,740,336	97,470	93,618
Median length of ORFs, nt	93	90	93	96	72
Median length of refORFs, nt	810	-	-	-	-

¹Before the elimination of refORFs

²After the elimination of refORFs

*Blastn searches against the NCBI non-redundant database and nucleotide alignments with annotated rRNA transcripts (Homology Group 1 in this manuscript) revealed that at least two transcripts annotated as ncRNA in the current *Medicago truncatula* genome (1.9) are actually rRNA transcripts. These two transcripts, MtrunA17_Chr0c01g0489091 and MtrunA17_Chr5g0421761, are considered as rRNA throughout the manuscript except for supplementary tables, which are meant to show the “history” of their annotation status.

[#]There are 875,356 non-refORFs (altORFs) of the given length range in total.

Supplementary Table S2. Statistics on altProts with at least one hit in the global BLASTP analysis before the application of the filter

Row	Statistic	mRNA	ncRNA	rRNA	tRNA
R1	Number of transcripts	44,624	5,657 [#]	62 [#]	974
R2	Number of altProts*	802,087	71,127	831	1,311
R3	Number of altProts that have at least one hit	13,427	4,398	392	426
R4	Percentage of altProts with at least one hit**	1.67	6.18	47.17	32.49
R5	AltProts per transcript (R3/R1)	0.30	0.78	6.32	0.44
R6	Transcripts per altProts (R1/R3)	3.32	1.29	0.16	2.29
R7	Median length of altProts with hit(s), aa	59.0	50.0	45.0	25.0
R8	Median length of alignment, aa	44.0	39.0	40.0	24.0
R9	Median % identity	78.0	88.5	93.3	100.0
R10	Median % query coverage	82.4	84.6	94.4	100.0

[#]Blastn searches against the NCBI non-redundant database and nucleotide alignments with annotated rRNA transcripts (Homology Group 1 in this manuscript) revealed that at least two transcripts annotated as ncRNA in the current *Medicago truncatula* genome (1.9) are actually rRNA transcripts. These two transcripts, MtrunA17_Chr0c01g0489091 and MtrunA17_Chr5g0421761, are considered as rRNA throughout the manuscript except for supplementary tables, which are meant to show the “history” of their annotation status.

*All theoretically possible altProts regardless of BLASTP results

**Percentage of altProts that have at least one hit per all altProts in the group (R3/R2*100)

Supplementary Table S3. Numbers of altProts before and after the elimination of queries with less than 70% identity to annotated proteins

Category	mRNA	ncRNA	rRNA	tRNA	Total
Total altProts with hits	13,427	4,398	392	426	18,643
Eliminated	4,709 (35%)	849 (19%)	7 (2%)	0 (0%)	5,565
Retained	8,718 (65%)	3,549 (81%)	385 (98%)	426 (100%)	13,078

Supplementary Table S4. Distribution of transcripts in different categories based on RNA type, cellular localization, mass spectrometry (MS) support of altORFs, and conservation of altORF translation products

Category	Total	mRNA	ncRNA	rRNA	tRNA	Nuclear transcripts	Mitochondrial transcripts	Chloroplast transcripts
Transcriptome	51,317	44,624	5,657	62	974	50,994	193*	130**
Transcripts with MS-supported altORFs	797	712	85	0	0	785	6	6
Transcripts with conserved altORFs (% identity \geq 70)	7,784	6,052	1,313	45	374	7,561	150	73
Transcripts with conserved or MS-supported altORFs	8,372	6,596	1,357	45	374	7,561	150	73
Transcripts with conserved and MS-supported altORFs***	211	168	41	0	0	199	6	6
Transcripts with modeled chimeric proteins	5,502	5,036	392	22	52	5,325	119	58
Transcripts with MS-supported chimeric proteins	145	129	12	3	1	131	7	7

*73 mRNA and 120 ncRNA

**86 mRNA, 34 ncRNA, 1 rRNA, and 9 tRNA

***These transcripts are both conserved and have at least one MS-supported altORF.

Supplementary Table S5. Redundant counts of chimeric protein models, shown per altProt type, transcript type, and programmed ribosomal frameshifting (PRF) value

PRF value	Modelled with MS-supported altProts	Modelled with conserved altProts	Sum	mRNA	ncRNA	rRNA	tRNA
+1	9,740	138,600	148,340	109,477	30,667	6,815	1,381
+2	8,752	130,865	139,617	102,661	29,005	6,009	1,942
-1	8,673	128,209	136,882	100,796	28,260	5,858	1,968
-2	9,355	134,127	143,482	105,972	29,607	6,525	1,378
Other (+1 to +10) #	16	1,768	1,784	1,110	540	134	0
Total	36,536	533,569	570,105	420,016	118,079	25,341	6,669
Total without other	36,520	531,801	568,321	418,906	117,539	25,207	6,669

#Adjacent altORFs separated by 1-10 nucleotides that can potentially be joined by PRF events with values +1 to +10.

Note that this category includes PRF values of +1 and +2 that are excluded from the four remaining categories.

Supplementary Table S6. Non-redundant counts of chimeric proteins modeled with altORFs that are MS-supported and conserved at the same time, shown per transcript type and PRF value

PRF value	Modelled with MS-supported and conserved at the same time	mRNA #	ncRNA	rRNA	tRNA
+1	930	930	0	0	0
+2	497	497	0	0	0
-1	487	487	0	0	0
-2	901	901	0	0	0
Other (+1 to +10) ^{##}	4	4	0	0	0
Total	2,819	2,819	0	0	0
Total without other	2,815	2,815	0	0	0

[#]All models in this table are restricted to mRNA because the definition of this category requires two overlapping or adjacent ORFs supported by MS. Since all canonical refORFs are assumed to be translated in mRNA by the genome annotation pipeline, there is a higher probability to find such models in the mRNA group.

^{##}Adjacent altORFs separated by 1-10 nucleotides that can potentially be joined by PRF events with values +1 to +10. Note that this category includes PRF values of +1 and +2 that are excluded from the four remaining categories.

Supplementary Table S7. Non-redundant counts of chimeric proteins modeled with MS-supported altORFs, shown per proteomic study and PRF value

PRF value	Modelled with MS-supported altProts (non-redundant) [#]	PXD002692 Marx et al., 2016	PXD013606 Shin et al., 2021	PXD022278 Castañeda et al., 2021
+1	9,740	8,067	974	1,321
+2	8,752	7,184	803	1,271
-1	8,673	7,120	800	1,256
-2	9,355	7,744	934	1,278
Other (+1 to +10) ^{##}	16	16	2	0
Total	36,536	30,131	3,513	5,126
Total without other	36,520	30,115	3,511	5,126

[#]All models in this table are restricted to mRNA because the definition of this category requires two overlapping or adjacent ORFs supported by MS. Since all canonical refORFs are assumed to be translated in mRNA by the genome annotation pipeline, there is a higher probability to find such models in the mRNA group.

^{##}Adjacent altORFs separated by 1-10 nucleotides that can potentially be joined by PRF events with values +1 to +10. Note that this category includes PRF values of +1 and +2 that are excluded from the four remaining categories.

Supplementary Table S8. Non-redundant counts of chimeric proteins modeled with conserved altORFs, shown per transcript type and PRF value

PRF value	mRNA	ncRNA	rRNA	tRNA
+1	90,089	17,889	4,574	815
+2	84,660	17,491	4,140	1,064
-1	83,100	17,087	4,046	1,090
-2	87,360	17,288	4,384	818
Other (+1 to +10) [#]	765	297	76	0
Total	345,974	70,052	17,220	3,787
Total without other	345,209	69,755	17,144	3,787

[#]Adjacent altORFs separated by 1-10 nucleotides that can potentially be joined by PRF events with values +1 to +10. Note that this category includes PRF values of +1 and +2 that are excluded from the four remaining categories.

Supplementary Table S9. Non-redundant counts of chimeric protein models, shown per altProt type, transcript type, and PRF value

PRF value	Modelled with MS-supported altProts	Modelled with conserved altProts #	Sum	mRNA	ncRNA	rRNA	tRNA
+1	9,740	113,367	122,177	98,899	17,889	4,574	815
+2	8,752	107,355	115,610	92,915	17,491	4,140	1,064
-1	8,673	105,323	113,509	91,286	17,087	4,046	1,090
-2	9,355	109,850	118,304	95,814	17,288	4,384	818
Other (+1 to +10) ##	16	1,138	1,150	777	297	76	0
Total	36,536	437,033	470,750	379,691	70,052	17,220	3,787
Total without other	36,520	435,895	469,600	378,914	69,755	17,144	3,787

#Counts of chimeric proteins modeled with altORFs that are MS-supported and conserved at the same time were subtracted from the “conserved” category. The redundancy due to altORF-altORF ambiguity (see the text in Section 4.3) concerns exclusively chimeric proteins modeled with conserved altORFs. This can be explained by the fact that the majority of PRF events that involve two altORFs instead of one altORF and one refORF are associated with non-mRNA transcript types, most of which have no MS-supported altORFs.

##Adjacent altORFs separated by 1-10 nucleotides that can potentially be joined by PRF events with values +1 to +10. Note that this category includes PRF values of +1 and +2 that are excluded from the four remaining categories.